
EFFECT OF CINNAMON AND HONEY ON ON-TIME AND OFF-TIME IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE: A CASE REPORT

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Abstract

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a slowly progressive neurodegenerative disease characterized by bradykinesia, rigidity, resting tremor, and postural instability. The progressive nature of the disease often leads to various troubles for the patient in walking and performing activities of daily living such as eating, bathing, and toileting. The oral dopaminergic medications help the patient to control motor and non-motor symptoms for some duration of time. It is imperative for the clinicians to maintain the on-time of the medication for which the clinician may change the dose and/or the frequency of administration of medicines. In this case report, a 71 years old female subject diagnosed with PD for more than 15 years. The cinnamon + honey therapy demonstrated clinical improvement in the "on-time" administered along with oral pharmacological medicine. The potential benefit of cinnamon may be due to neurotrophic, neuroprotective and anti-neuroinflammation properties of cinnamon in neuronal and glial cells of the brain. However, high quality controlled trials are warranted further to evaluate the potential benefit of cinnamon in the treatment patient with PD.

Keywords: *cinnamon, honey, on-time, off-time, Parkinson's disease and exercise*

INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) or Shaking Palsy is common progressive, neurodegenerative disorder [1] caused by insufficient or lack production of a neurotransmitter, the dopamine from the substantia nigra and basal ganglia which plans and controls the body movements characterized by bradykinesia, rigidity, resting tremor and postural instability [2]. Since the PD is a progressive disease, the symptoms begin gradually, starting from one side of the body

and proceeds to affect the other sides. The progressive nature of the disease often leads to various troubles for the patient in walking and performing activities of daily living such as eating, bathing, and toileting. In addition to these problems, the subjects with PD often experience depression, disturbed sleep, trouble in chewing, swallowing and speaking. The impairment and disability associated with PD required a multidisciplinary approach for effective management to maintain subject's daily activity of life and life expectancy. Hughes et al (1992) suggested that therapy should be focused on improving motor impairment and improving the disability associated with PD in the early and late stages of the diseases respectively [1]. Therefore, the subject with PD warrants high-quality care that includes oral medication, physiotherapy, educational and environmental modifications, psychotherapy and surgery.

The oral dopaminergic medications help the patient to control motor and non-motor symptoms for some duration of time. This time of controlled symptoms is called on-time under the influence of medication whereas the off-time is when the medication remains no longer effective and the symptoms such as intension tremor, bradykinesia and rigidity reappears. Maintaining the optimal on-time crucial for physiotherapeutic intervention for improving muscle strength and mobility. However, as the disease progresses the oral dopaminergic medications fail to prevent the symptoms from occurring before the next dose of a medication called "wearing-Off" [3]. The time duration in between the worsening of symptoms and the next dose taken is known as Off time. Therefore, the overall aim of oral medication therapy is to improve or maintain the on-time and minimize the off-time and wearing off times. Furthermore, the medication would also have aimed to improve the muscle tone, intensity, and frequency of dyskinesia and postural instability/freezing.

It is imperative for the clinicians to maintain the on-time of the medication for which they may adopt the change in dose and frequency of administration of medicines or change medication (another dopamine agonist) and/or combination therapy (levodopa / Carbidopa+ entacapone) [4]. In addition, emerging literature in the field of alternative medicine has been proved to be effective in the management of PD related symptoms. Therefore, this case report describe the effect of cinnamon and honey therapy improves the on-time in a subject with PD treated along with oral medications.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 71-year-old female subject diagnosed with PD was referred to the author for the management of severe whole-body weakness and tremors in both upper limbs and lower limbs in rest and history of frequent falls. Based on the physical assessment, the patient demonstrated severe weakness in both upper and lower limbs and trunk muscles and the patient demonstrated difficulty in doing activities of daily living due to tremors affecting both upper and lower limbs. The subject reported frequent falls in the past years because of the tremors and associated muscle weakness. In addition, she reported that earlier physiotherapeutic management did not make any significant improvement in her physical and

functional status. The subject was taking the oral medication with Carbidopa anhydrous 25 mg, Levodopa IP 100 mg and Entacapone BP 200 mg three times a day.

Patient History

The subject was clinically diagnosed as Parkinson’s patient in 2002 but she has not started medication or physiotherapeutic management for 12 months. In 2003, she was put on oral medications with Carbidopa anhydrous 25 mg, Levodopa IP 100 mg and Entacapone BP 200 mg three times a day. However, the subject did not undergo any form of physiotherapy or physical exercise during initial oral medication, thus made the patient very weak and became dependent on others for her regular activities of daily living and functions. Consequently, the subject started a short course of acupressure therapy for 3 months that made some improvement in her status and started walking inside the house. After 12 months, she underwent few short courses of home-based physiotherapy based exercise intervention and further treated with longterm home-based physiotherapeutic inventions. The supervised physiotherapy session with the physiotherapist demonstrated functional improvement in muscle strength and mobility of limbs and trunk. During the physiotherapeutic intervention, the subject was taking oral medications every four hours and reported an “on-time” of four hours. After three subsequent years of therapy, the subject reported the duration of off time was getting reduced that compelled the physician to increase the frequency of medication four times a day i.e. after every 3 hours with an increased dose of Carbidopa anhydrous from 25mg to 35mg. However, changes in the frequency and dosage of medication did not make significant improvements in the off-time of the subject. Furthermore, the changes in the off-time period from 3 to 2 hour negatively affect physiotherapeutic intervention as the recurrence of symptoms make difficulty for the patient to perform the desired joint movement and exercise regime (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Parkinson’s symptom diary to record on- and off-time, falls and dyskinesias during pre-cinnamon + honey therapy.

Figure 2. Parkinson's symptom diary to record on- and off-time, falls and dyskinesias during post-cinnamon + honey therapy

Cinnamon and Honey Dose

The subject was advised to take ¼ teaspoon of powdered cinnamon and ½ teaspoon of honey (combination) twice a day for eight weeks along with oral antiparkinson medications and home physiotherapy management.

Results: Changes in "On-time & Off-time" duration

At the end of the first week of cinnamon + honey therapy, the subject reported improvement in general feeling and better "on-time". The subject also reported a reduction in off-time along with increased On-time for more than 2 hours. Furthermore, the subject demonstrated a significant reduction in off-time and increased on-time for three hours in the four weeks. The subject was further assessed for on-time and off-time at the end of eight weeks and found the on-time was improved for three and a half hours. It was also noticed that there was no deterioration or improvement in on-time / off-time at the end of 8 weeks and the on-time remained stable at three and a half an hour (Figure 2).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In routine clinical practice, the pharmacological management, the drug choice, dose and frequency of administration for a newly subject with PD required careful analysis of a number of elements including disease stage (acute or chronic), symptoms (bradykinesia, tremor & altered tone), age, level of physical disability and function activity and psychosocial issues. The medication such as Levodopa, dopamine agonist, MAO-B (monoamine Oxidase-B) inhibitors, Catechol O-methyltransferase (COMT) inhibitor, Anticholinergics, and Amantadine are the commonly prescribed pharmacological agents for the management of PD. Although there is no permanent cure for the PD, these medications provide the symptomatic reliefs for symptoms of PD. Since the long term administration of

pharmacological medication often associated with various side effects and reduced on-time and wearing-off, it is recommended to employ other various non-pharmacological and alternative medicine as an adjunct therapy for the PD along with routine pharmacological agents.

Cinnamon is a natural spice and has been used for the management of gastrointestinal problems and diabetic in the field of traditional medicine. Literature reported that oral administration of powdered cinnamon acts as neuroprotective, anti-neuroinflammation and neurotrophic agents which protects the dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra [5]. Cinnamon helps to protect the dopaminergic neuronal, normalized striatal neurotransmitters and improves motor function in PD [4]. Pahan and Pahan reported mechanism of cinnamon action on the neuronal and glial cells in the brain. They postulated that the cinnamon is metabolized into sodium benzoate (NaB) in the liver. In the brain, NaB increases the production of neurotrophic factors, BDNF via activation of protein kinase A and cAMP. In addition, NaB also inhibits the activation of p21ras, a small G protein and thereby attenuates the activation of nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B) and the expression of NF- κ B-dependent proinflammatory molecules leading to anti-inflammation. Following the suppression of NF- κ B activation, the expression of inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) also goes down and the production of nitric oxide is reduced which ultimately restores/upregulates the level of neuroprotective proteins like DJ-1 and Parkin [5-6]. Our present case report also showed the reduction in Off-time and increase in On-time with the cinnamon and honey. In conclusion, the neurotrophic, neuroprotective and anti-neuroinflammation properties of cinnamon may be potential adjunct therapy for effective management for PD along with other pharmacological agents. However, it is recommended for a high degree controlled trials are necessary with the optimal sample size to evaluate the significant role of cinnamon for the management of PD.